

FILTER-BASED CUCKOO OPTIMIZATION ALGORITHM FOR FEATURE SELECTION

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Abstract

Majority of the stored data contain irrelevant and redundant features that affect the classification performance. Therefore, feature selection (FS) is essential to remove both the redundant and irrelevant features and consequently improved the classification performance. FS can be either filter or wrapper. In wrapper FS, a classifier is used to measure the accuracy of the selected features but its computationally expensive and not favourable on large dimensional datasets. While, filters are computationally cheap and can scale up to large dimensional data sets but do not consider the relationship between selected features. Information theory is one of the filter approaches that is used to measure the relationship between selected features and the target class. Evolutionary algorithms have been widely used to search for the relevant number of features in different FS problems. Cuckoo optimization algorithm (COA) is among the recent evolutionary algorithm with proven records as a search technique due to its fast convergence and robustness but has limited application in FS. In this study, a filter-based feature selection using COA along with information theory is proposed. Out of the two basic concepts of information theory mutual information and entropy, the former will serve as the fitness function that will evaluate the feature subsets. Therefore, the proposed COA-MI will use a deep belief network (DBN) as the classifier on some data sets to measure the performance of the proposed tech-

nique in terms of selected features, accuracy, and computation time.

1 INTRODUCTION

The rate at which data is growing exponentially in various field has led to significance increase in the dimensionality of the stored data. This create a serious issue in analysing and studying the pattern of the data in other to make a promising decision. This is because some of the stored data contain irrelevant and redundant features that create a problem toward description of the target class and consequently affect the performance of the classification algorithm. Feature selection (FS) is one of the data mining pre-processing steps that is used to remove both redundant and irrelevant feature from a data set. In addition to improving performance of the classification algorithm, FS can also reduce the computational time of the classifier [1].

According to class label, FS is divided in to two; supervised and non-supervised. In supervised FS the class label of the data is known in advanced unlike in the non-supervised where the class label is unknown. The two major alarming issues of a FS are (1. how to search for the best subset of features and (2. how to evaluate the best subset generated [2]. In searching for the best subset of features. Three search strategies are normally used [4]; complete search, sequential or heuristic search and random search. Out of all these search strategies, random search

is the only one that can escape from local optima in the search space due to the use of randomness [2]. Therefore, in this study, the random search strategy will be adopted as well. The second issue of FS is selecting the optimal subset of features. This basically depends on the FS model either filter or wrapper. The filter FS is computationally fast and can scale up to high dimensional data set. In addition, its evaluation is based on the intrinsic behaviour, dependency and characteristics of the data. In contrast to the wrapper FS that depends on classification algorithms for evaluating the subsets of features selected [3]. In other to demonstrate the efficiency of feature selection particularly on high dimensional data sets the filter-based FS will be adopted. There are various evaluation techniques for the filter FS such as distance measure, information measures, dependency measure and consistency measure among others. Information theory or information measure is one of the most significant theories that can measure the relevance between two features and their class labels during feature ranking process [4].

Mutual Information (MI) is the measure of dependence between random variables by providing a way to evaluate the relevance of the feature subset. MI can be consider as the most favourite and commonly applied for filters owed to two main properties: a) Measuring various types of relationship between variables and b) Preserving firmness under transformations in the feature space that are invertible and differentiable.

Battiti, [5] developed mutual information feature selection (MIFS) method and categorized the features as relevant and redundant. Redundant features are features with low information content or high redundancy. A heuristic function was employed to control and balance between the relevance and redundant features. Lastly, features are selected in greedy manner. Other typical examples of MI based approaches are maximum relevance and minimum redundancy (mRMR) along with uniformly improved mutual information feature selection (MIFS-U) and conditional mutual information maximization (CMIM). Even though,

they are easy to implement as well as minimize the number of features. However, the selected features cannot be removed or altered in advanced because of their static greedy search mechanism [4].

To address these difficulties, scholars are inspired to design a mutual information-based filter approaches with metaheuristic algorithms because of their global search capability. Recently, metaheuristic algorithms such as, genetic algorithms (GAs), particle swarm optimization (PSO), ant colony optimization (ACO), and differential evolution (DE) have been used for FS using MI. In addition, artificial bee colony, bacterial colony optimization and cuckoo search algorithm have also been studied to attain improved feature subsets for various classification problems using information theory as well as other measures.

This clearly showed that using metaheuristic algorithms with MI is gaining popularity particularly for filter-based FS. In addition, there are still other metaheuristic algorithms such as cuckoo optimization algorithm that showed a promising result and however not investigated for FS especially using information theory. In this study, COA [6] will be adapted and used with mutual information COA-MI for feature selection. COA is chosen for FS due to its simplicity, fast convergence rate, global search ability and easy to implements.

2 PROPOSED WORK

2.1 Cuckoo Optimization Algorithm

Rajabioun in [6] presented a new evolutionary optimization algorithm named cuckoo optimization algorithm (COA) that is also, stimulated by the habits of a bird family known as cuckoo. How they place egg and upbringing behaviour of the cuckoos are also the foundation behind this innovative optimization algorithm. The standard COA is shown in Algorithm 1 below.

Algorithm 1 Cuckoo optimization algorithm pseudocode

- 1: **Begin**
 - 2: Set cuckoo environments through some arbitrary ideas on the global function
 - 3: Devote some eggs roughly to respectively cuckoos
 - 4: Explain ELR for every single cuckoo
 - 5: Allow the cuckoos to lay their eggs in their matching ELR
 - 6: Destroy those cuckoos familiar by the multitude birds
 - 7: Allow egg to incubate and baby chicken raise
 - 8: Estimate the environment of every recently grownup cuckoo
 - 9: Restricts cuckoos' highest figure in location and destroy those who exist in inferior environments
 - 10: Group cuckoos and discover finest cluster and choose goal line environment
 - 11: Allow the fresh cuckoo populace to settle at the goal line environment
 - 12: If halt criteria is fulfilled halt, otherwise go to 3
 - 13: **End**
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2.2 Cuckoo Optimization Algorithm Based Mutual Information COA-MI

COA Based Mutual Information for Feature Selection (COA-MI) Mutual information is defined as the measure of dependence between two random variables or features by providing a way to evaluate the relevance of the feature subset and the class label. Consider a discrete feature subset X with m selected features $X = (x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_m)$ and a class label C , the relevancy between X and C is defined in 1 as shown below.

$$Relev_{mi}(X; C) = \max \sum_i I(x; c) \quad (1)$$

Where $I(x; c)$ stands for the mutual information between x and c . Its imperative to remove redundancy among selected features. According to mutual information, the redundancy in X and Y can be defined as shown in 2 below.

$$Redun_{mi}(X; Y) = \min \left(\frac{1}{|m|} \sum_{i,j} I(x_i; y_j) \right) \quad (2)$$

To get the required maximum relevance and minimum redundancy both $Relev_{mi}$ and $Redun_{mi}$ should be used when evaluating the goodness of m . Therefore, a β constant value in $[1, 0]$ is introduced to sum up the relevance and redundancy. Although, there is need to remove the redundancy

from the relevance after their summation with a β constant multiplier and hence the fitness function will be same in 3 below

$$Fitness_{mi} = \beta (Relev_{mi} + Redun_{mi}) - Redun_{mi} \quad (3)$$

Hence, 3 will be applied on COA-MI to direct the evolutionary search process of the COA to search for the best feature subsets depending on the value of β . The computation of $I(x; c)$ and $I(x_i; y_j)$ can be obtained in 4 and 5. The $Fitness_{mi}$ is a maximization function targeting to take the full advantage of the relevance and concurrently reduce the redundancy in m .

$$I(X; Y) = - \sum_{i,j} P(x_i, y_j) \log_2 P \left(\frac{P(x_i, y_j)}{P(x_i) \cdot P(y_j)} \right) \quad (4)$$

$$H(X, Y) = - \sum_{i,j} P(x_i, y_j) \log_2 P(x_i, y_j) \quad (5)$$

2.3 Proposed Pseudocode of COA-MI

The proposed COA-MI pseudocode is shown in Algorithm 2 below. The proposed COA-MI is a maximization function that will evaluate the goodness of the ranked features and measure the interaction between variable to improve generality of the selected features. Deep belief network will be used to measure the classification accuracy on some data sets.

Algorithm 2 Proposed COA-MI pseudocode

- 1: **Begin**
 - 2: Initialise each habitat with some features from a data set
 - 3: Collect the features in their respective habitats
 - 4: Explain ELR for every single cuckoo
 - 5: Allow the cuckoos to lay their eggs in their matching ELR
 - 6: Destroy those cuckoos familiar by the multitude birds
 - 7: Allow egg to incubate and baby chicken raise
 - 8: Estimate the environment of every recently grownup cuckoo
 - 9: Restricts cuckoos' highest figure in location and destroy those who exist in inferior environments
 - 10: Group cuckoos and discover finest cluster and choose goal line environment
 - 11: Allow the fresh cuckoo populace to settle at the goal line environment
 - 12: Return the optimum solution (selected features)
 - 13: Evaluate the fitness function according to $Fitness_{mi} = \beta (Relev_{mi} + Redun_{mi}) - Redun_{mi}$ equation 3
 - 14: If halt criteria is fulfilled halt, otherwise go to 2
 - 15: **End**
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